

Comparison of the FAST and NDAC iterated sphere solutions

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1. Introduction

This note describes the results of a comparison made between the FAST iterated 18 months sphere solution (tape received on 30 June) and the 18 months NDAC solution identified as #136 (computed on 14 October 1992). It supersedes the comparison made in November 1992 between the same NDAC solution and the 'non-iterated' FAST solution. The present solutions are reasonably comparable in terms of the iteration phases of the two consortia: they are both based on great-circle solutions performed with a star catalogue already improved by space data to the extent that attitude and projection errors should be almost negligible.

FAST and NDAC have used slightly different acceptance criteria for defining which stars that go into the comparison. The FAST solution thus contains a total of 93612 accepted stars, while the NDAC solution contains 102411 stars. They contain 90630 stars in common. Clearly the FAST criterion is more stringent, which may to some part explain the higher overall quality of the FAST parallaxes found in Section 8.

2. Calculation of orientation differences

The comparison of positions and proper motions requires that the reference frames of the various sources (e.g., FAST, NDAC, FK5) agree as to their global orientation and rotation. Thus, one of the first things to do is to determine the global orientation differences of the catalogues.

At the arbitrary epoch t the orientation of catalogue B with respect to catalogue A is given by the (small) rotation vector $\mathbf{r}(t)$ needed to bring a reference frame originally aligned with A into coincidence with B . The components of $\mathbf{r}(t)$ may be expressed in any reference frame (e.g., ecliptic or galactic coordinates). In the following we assume that the components r_x, r_y, r_z refer to either A or B , the difference being negligible as long as $|\mathbf{r}|$ is less than an arcsec. With T_A, T_B denoting the epochs of the catalogues we have to first order:

$$[\alpha_B(t) - \alpha_A(t)] \cos \delta = [r_x(t) \cos \alpha + r_y(t) \sin \alpha] \sin \delta - r_z(t) \cos \delta \quad (1a)$$

$$\delta_B(t) - \delta_A(t) = -r_x(t) \sin \alpha + r_y(t) \cos \alpha \quad (1b)$$

where $\alpha_A(t) = \alpha_A(T_A) + (t - T_A)\mu_{\alpha A}$, $\delta_A(t) = \delta_A(T_A) + (t - T_A)\mu_{\delta A}$, and similarly for B . Differentiation yields, with $\mathbf{v} = \dot{\mathbf{r}}$:

$$(\mu_{\alpha B} - \mu_{\alpha A}) \cos \delta = (v_x \cos \alpha + v_y \sin \alpha) \sin \delta - v_z \cos \delta \quad (2a)$$

$$\mu_{\delta B} - \mu_{\delta A} = -v_x \sin \alpha + v_y \cos \alpha. \quad (2b)$$

Since the proper motion differences are fixed it follows that $\mathbf{v}$ is constant and we can write

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{r}(T) + (t - T)\mathbf{v} \quad (3)$$

where T is some convenient epoch of comparison. Clearly $\mathbf{r}(T)$ and $\mathbf{v}$ can be estimated independently from (1) (with $t = T$) and (2); the resulting $\mathbf{r}(t)$ should in principle not depend on the choice of T . In the following we choose $T = 90.75$, close to the mean epoch of observation, so that $\mathbf{r}(T)$ closely represents the ‘best’ agreement between the two positional systems.

The estimation of $\mathbf{r}(T)$ and $\mathbf{v}$ from (1) and (2) could be done by ordinary least-squares (minimization of the L2 norm). For robustness we prefer however to use the L1 norm. Given the set of stars for which the comparison should be made, the actual procedure is as follows. The stars are divided in eight subsets, usually by putting the 1st, 9th, 17th, ... star in the first subset and the 2nd, 10th, 18th, ... in the second, etc. Independent L1-norm estimates of $\mathbf{r}(T)$ and $\mathbf{v}$ are then made for each subset. The final estimate is the mean of the eight solutions, with the sample standard deviation between the solutions, divided by $\sqrt{8}$, as an estimate of the uncertainty of the mean. It should be noted that the relative uncertainty of the standard deviations, due to the small sample size of eight, is as much as 25%. The rms residual of the fit is robustly estimated as $\sqrt{\pi/2}$ times the average absolute residual.

3. Orientation differences NDAC–FAST

Using $T = 90.75$ as comparison epoch, the overall difference between the reference frames of the FAST (A) and NDAC (B) solutions is found to be:

$$\mathbf{r}(90.75) = \begin{pmatrix} +15.568 \pm 0.006 \\ +13.835 \pm 0.004 \\ -11.414 \pm 0.006 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mas}, \quad \mathbf{v} = \begin{pmatrix} +0.676 \pm 0.012 \\ -4.203 \pm 0.012 \\ +5.049 \pm 0.021 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mas yr}^{-1}. \quad (4)$$

The rms residuals of (1) and (2) are 1.70 mas and 3.42 mas yr⁻¹, respectively. The corresponding rms residuals obtained in November, using the non-iterated FAST solution, were 2.19 mas and 4.02 mas yr⁻¹, so the agreement is indeed significantly better now.

The global consistency of the solutions can be tested by estimating $\mathbf{r}(t)$ independently for different subsets of stars, e.g., according to their positions, magnitudes and colours. Ideally the different vectors should agree to within their standard errors.

3.1. Orientation differences versus position

If the sky is divided in octants we obtain the following estimates for $T = 90.75$ [Table 1]:

α	δ	N	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
0 – 90°	+	9991	15.516	13.790	-11.445	0.703	-4.293	5.024
90 – 180°	+	10400	15.627	13.813	-11.419	0.664	-4.358	4.994
180 – 270°	+	10685	15.548	13.778	-11.344	0.811	-3.971	4.871
270 – 360°	+	12500	15.528	13.912	-11.477	0.777	-4.210	5.295
0 – 90°	-	10557	15.511	13.740	-11.360	0.787	-4.204	4.911
90 – 180°	-	13237	15.498	13.918	-11.514	0.851	-4.356	5.211
180 – 270°	-	11806	15.441	13.775	-11.561	0.671	-4.137	5.060
270 – 360°	-	11454	15.663	13.813	-11.394	0.541	-4.201	4.830
mean value			15.542	13.817	-11.439	0.726	-4.216	5.024
standard deviation			0.067	0.060	0.070	0.094	0.119	0.152

The average estimated uncertainty is 0.020 mas in the components of $\mathbf{r}(T)$ and 0.047 mas yr⁻¹ in $\mathbf{v}$. Thus the rms dispersion between the octants is roughly three times greater than ideally expected. The discrepancy, of the order of 0.06 mas in position and 0.1 mas yr⁻¹ in proper motion, can be regarded as a measure of the internal consistency of the FAST and NDAC solutions on a global ($\sim 90^\circ$ arc length) level.

3.2. Orientation differences versus magnitude

Dividing into bright and faint stars we find no decidedly significant effect [Table 2]:

	N	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
$H_p < 8.5$	46255	15.551 ± 0.007	13.839 ± 0.007	-11.413 ± 0.007	0.706 ± 0.009	-4.242 ± 0.021	5.048 ± 0.028
$H_p > 8.5$	44375	15.588 ± 0.011	13.830 ± 0.006	-11.418 ± 0.010	0.641 ± 0.025	-4.165 ± 0.018	5.046 ± 0.031
(diff)/(total s.d.)		-2.8	+1.0	+0.4	+2.4	-2.8	+0.0

3.3. Orientation differences versus colour

Separating the stars according to colour we find [Table 3]:

	N	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
$B-V < 0.7$	46518	15.372 ± 0.005	13.909 ± 0.007	-11.436 ± 0.008	0.959 ± 0.012	-4.291 ± 0.014	5.086 ± 0.028
$B-V > 0.7$	44112	15.793 ± 0.007	13.760 ± 0.009	-11.461 ± 0.010	0.346 ± 0.028	-4.105 ± 0.014	5.027 ± 0.025
(diff)/(total s.d.)		-49	+13	+2	+20	-9	+2

There is clearly a very significant colour effect, which is practically the same as observed in the November data. This is a surprise: at that time the effect was attributed to the non-iterated FAST solution using a fixed global chromaticity parameter (whereas a linear time variation was assumed in the NDAC solution). The iterated FAST solution includes the linear variation of the chromaticity (?), and so this effect should have disappeared in the present comparison.

4. Orientation differences relative to FK5

The orientation of the FAST and NDAC solutions with respect to FK5 are given in the table below. Only the 1245 stars in common to FAST, NDAC and FK5 were used. As before the epoch of comparison is $T = 90.75$ [Table 5]:

	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
FAST - FK5	4.727	19.499	-35.145	-0.254	3.354	-5.625
NDAC - FK5	20.871	33.578	-46.274	0.646	-0.983	-0.633
difference (N-F)	16.144	14.079	-11.129	0.900	-4.337	4.992

The uncertainties in the components of $\mathbf{r}(T)$ and $\mathbf{v}$ are 3.1 mas and 0.11 mas yr⁻¹. The rms residuals are 93.3 mas and 4.0 mas yr⁻¹.

The last line in the table gives the difference (NDAC - FK5) - (FAST - FK5). Note that this is not exactly the same as the (NDAC - FAST) orientation difference in (4). Thus, if we want to put the FAST and NDAC catalogues on a common, quasi-FK5 system (let us call it H18), it is not sufficient just to rotate by the respective differences relative to FK5. Rather, we should adopt rotations which are rigorously consistent with the (much better defined) differences in (4). The following rotations could be used [Table 6]:

	r_x	r_y	r_z	v_x	v_y	v_z
FAST - H18:	5.015	19.621	-35.003	-0.142	3.287	-5.654
NDAC - H18:	20.583	33.456	-46.417	0.534	-0.916	-0.605
difference (N-F)	15.568	13.835	-11.414	0.676	-4.203	5.049

5. Position and proper motion differences after rotation

Fig. 1 shows the distributions of individual NDAC-FAST differences in α and δ at $T = 90.75$ after elimination of the orientation difference in (4). The maximum total difference $(\Delta\alpha^2 \cos^2 \delta + \Delta\delta^2)^{1/2}$ is 1335 mas. In fact, for 22 stars the difference is in the range 1206 to 1335 mas, indicating a grid-step error in either solution; if these stars are excluded the maximum total difference is 58 mas.

For $\Delta\alpha \cos \delta$ the median value is $+0.002 \pm 0.005$ mas and the standard deviation 1.636 mas (after trimming away 250 points beyond $\pm 4.8\sigma$)*. For $\Delta\delta$ the median is $+0.005 \pm 0.005$ and the standard deviation 1.359 mas (213 points trimmed).

Fig. 2 shows the corresponding distributions of individual proper motion differences after rotation by (4). In $\mu_\alpha \cos \delta$ the median difference is $+0.002 \pm 0.013$ mas yr⁻¹ and the standard deviation 3.857 mas yr⁻¹ (321 points trimmed). In μ_δ the median difference is -0.016 ± 0.012 mas yr⁻¹ and standard deviation 3.248 mas yr⁻¹ (305 points trimmed).

* The trim limit is calculated as $\sqrt{2 \ln N}$ times the (trimmed) sample standard deviation, where $N = 90630$ is the total number of data points. For a normal distribution one would not expect to find points beyond this limit.

Fig. 3-4 show the position and proper motion differences averaged in areas of $7.5 \times 7.5 \text{ deg}^2$. There are clearly correlated differences in areas of this size, especially in the ecliptical region, but on the whole there are no clear systematics.

6. Parallax differences

Histogram and variations with position are shown in Figs 5-6. The median difference (NDAC-FAST) is $-0.008 \pm 0.007 \text{ mas}$ and the standard deviation 1.956 mas (137 points trimmed).

If the stars are divided in equal halves according to δ , H_p and $B_T - V_T$, the differences in (NDAC-FAST) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{north} - \text{south} &= -0.052 \pm 0.014 \text{ mas} \\ \text{bright} - \text{faint} &= -0.050 \pm 0.014 \text{ mas} \\ \text{blue} - \text{red} &= +0.007 \pm 0.014 \text{ mas} \end{aligned}$$

In November the north-south asymmetry was $-0.012 \pm 0.014 \text{ mas}$. The present value is not alarming but should hopefully disappear in future solutions. The same can be said about the brightness effect.

7. Formal errors

On the the parallax and proper motion errors are analyzed. Histograms and scatter plots of the overall distributions are shown in Figs 7 and 8. The histograms are remarkably similar, only with a shift (or scaling) of about 15% in both parameters. The median formal errors are 1.705 mas and $3.258 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ for FAST, 1.956 mas and $3.679 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$ for NDAC.

The scatter plots (Fig. 8) are not symmetric about the diagonal, but there is an excess of stars with $\sigma_N < \sigma_F$. At the moment I have no explanation for this. It is not clearly related to the magnitude or the number of observations per star.

8. Parallax distributions

The distributions of the parallaxes (for the 90630 stars common to FAST and NDAC) are shown in Fig. 9, together with that of a weighted mean ($0.6\pi_F + 0.4\pi_N$). Clearly the latter is significantly better than either individual solution. The relative merit of different weightings can be judged from the number of negative parallaxes [Table 7]:

w_{FAST}	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
w_{NDAC}	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.0
$N(\pi < 0)$	6352	6007	5681	5447	5295	5227	5223	5290	5453	5734	5977

If we adopt a median external error of 2.0 mas for the NDAC parallaxes, then (using the method of NDAC/LO/142, Section 4) it follows that the corresponding number for FAST is 1.8 mas , and for the weighted mean 1.6 mas . Thus it appears that the actual FAST errors are about 10% smaller, on average, than the NDAC errors. This is also reflected in the formal errors (Fig. 7), although the difference there is a bit more larger. This could be explained if the FAST formal errors are slightly underestimated (by up to 5%).

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FIG. 2

Position differences NDAC - FAST (18 months)

ndac

1993 Jul 8

FIG. 3

P.M. differences NDAC - FAST (18 months)

ndac

1993 Jul 8

FIG. 4

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

FIG. 8

FIG. 9